

PHILOLOGY

A COMPARATIVE QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF CHATGPT MODELS AND HUMAN TRANSLATION OF SCIENTIFIC TEXTS

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Abstract

This paper aims to examine and compare translations of scientific texts from English to Russian performed by ChatGPT-3.5, ChatGPT-4, and human translators. The study conducts a comparative quality analysis of these translations and utilizes the neural-based machine translation evaluation metrics COMET-22 and BLEURT-20.

A key aspect of this paper is to identify errors, shedding the light on the strengths and limitations of both the deep learning based language models in order to better estimate their performance in comparison to human translation.

Using a mixed-method research approach, this study analyzed 30 scientific articles in English language assessing the efficiency of automated translation systems.

Keywords: AI (Artificial Intelligence), natural language processing (NLP), COMET-22, BLEURT-20 metrics, ChatGPT models, translation, human translation

Introduction. The development of world's technologies has seen remarkable progress in the natural language processing (NLP) and automatic evaluation metrics as well.

Lately advancements, in natural language processing (NLP) have been quite impressive leading to the creation of the language models such as ChatGPT. These deep learning-based models have demonstrated proficiency, in translation activities sparking a lot of enthusiasm among researchers. Particularly, in the area of machine translation, these models have shown tremendous promise.

Machine translation serves to connect people across languages enabling the exchange of information, in the scientific community. The accurate and swift translation of content, into languages plays a role in fostering cooperation enhancing cultural awareness and speeding up progress, in scientific fields.

With the increasing acknowledgment and usefulness of ChatGPT 4 in translation it is vital to subject this language model to evaluation and comparison with human translations. Understanding the strengths and weaknesses of ChatGPT 4 in handling content is essential for leveraging its capabilities ethically.

As AI language models reshape the translation landscape grasping their potentials and constraints becomes crucial for making informed decisions on integrating them into scientific workflows. AIs role in translating texts is highly valuable as it facilitates a streamlined and accessible global exchange of scientific knowledge.

The history of neural networks

The history of networks spans, over years and has experienced significant progress in both theoretical and practical domains. A neural network is a method in machine learning that processes inputs to forecast outputs. While they share similarities, with machine learning approaches they possess strengths.

Linear models are a core element of statistical machine translation. A potential translation x of a sentence is represented by a set of features $h_i(x)$. Each feature is weighted by a parameter λ_i to obtain an overall score [1].

Neural networks are mathematical models that use learning algorithms inspired by the brain to process information. Since neural networks are used in computers, they are collectively called as "artificial neural networks" (ANNs) [2]. It consists of layers of interconnected nodes, known as neurons, organized in different layers, such as input, hidden, and output layers. Each neuron performs simple computations on its input data and passes the results to other neurons.

Neural networks modify linear models in two important ways. The first is the use of multiple layers. Instead of computing the output value directly from the input values, a hidden layer is introduced. It is called hidden, due to inputs and outputs in training instances, but not the mechanism that connects them — this use of the concept hidden is similar to its meaning in hidden Markov models [3].

Deep Learning

The progress of deep learning technology has unveiled revelations and advancements that have significantly propelled the realm of intelligence research. As time has passed the field has undergone changes that mirror the viewpoints and inputs from a range of researchers.

The advancement of deep learning technology has provided valuable insights and technological breakthroughs that have significantly shaped the field of artificial intelligence research.

The history of learning is commonly categorized into three stages; Cybernetics (1940s-1960s) Connectionism (1980s-1990s) and Deep Learning (from 2006 to the present) [4, 5].

Looking back at the emergence of cybernetics it was a period characterized by the exploration of networks. In 1943 Warren McCulloch and Walter Pitts introduced a model for networks establishing a foundation for future advancements. In the 1950s 1960s Frank Rosenblatt developed the Perceptron, a network designed to mimic human thought processes.

Interest in networks experienced a resurgence in the 1980s with the rise of connectionism. Notable progress during this era included the introduction of the backpropagation algorithm by Rumelhart, Hinton and Williams in 1986 enabling. Neural networks to learn from complex datasets. This period also witnessed the development of models and algorithms such, as Hopfield networks and Boltzmann machines contributing to both theoretical understanding and practical applications of neural networks.

The modern era of deep learning began in 2006 when Geoffrey Hinton demonstrated that pre-training layers of neural network one at a time could significantly improve the training processes for deep neural networks. This discovery, along with the increasing availability of large data sets and powerful GPU (Graphics Processing Units), led to major breakthroughs. By 2012, Alex Krizhevsky, Ilya Sutskever, and Geoffrey Hinton [6] made a landmark achievement with their AlexNet model, which drastically outperformed other competitors in the ImageNet competition, reducing the error rate by a substantial margin.

Since then, deep learning has seen exponential growth in interest and application, influencing multiple fields such as autonomous driving, natural language processing, and medical diagnosis. Organizations like OpenAI have been at the forefront, pushing the boundaries with models like GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer), which showcases the capabilities of deep

learning in understanding and generating human-like text. Additionally, the research organization OpenAI uses deep learning technology to build all generative models, leveraging large amounts of data to train AI systems to perform various tasks [7].

The field of translation has been remarkable advancement with systems like ChatGPT compared to traditional human translation efforts. These AI-driven tools leverage deep learning to interpret and generate text across different languages, achieving near-human or superior performance in terms of speed and scalability, though they may still face challenges with nuances and context-specific interpretations [8, 9, 10].

Metrics

Neural machine translation (NMT) utilizes Transformer-based deep learning, has advanced rapidly current years [11]. Unlike statistical machine translation, NMT uses neural network to generate more varied sentences. However, evaluating the quality of these translations is essential but challenging. Due to linguistic variability there is no single correct translation, making human evaluation subjective and inappropriate. Human and automated evaluation considered as main approaches to assessing the machine translation systems.

As we know human evaluation effective and considered the gold standard in natural language generation but also expensive and requires substantial human labor. Automated evaluations are more cost-effective and easy used for comparative analysis but have limitations.

Automated metrics are evolving to better mimic human assessment by incorporating advanced machine learning techniques, including those based on deep learning models like Transformers. These metrics generally fall into several categories: lexical-based, embedding-based, and supervised metrics.

Figure 1. Taxonomy of automatic evaluation metrics.

The first well-known evaluation metric for machine translation, BLEU (Bilingual Evaluation Understudy) was introduced in 2002 [12]. BLEU was developed by researchers at IBM and quickly became a standard for evaluating the quality of text translated by machine translation systems. It compares the candidate translation of text to one or more reference translations, measuring the precision of matched sequences of word or phrases. BLEU was pioneering due to one of the first metrics provided a quantitative way to assess the qual-

ity of machine-translated text, allowing for more systematic and reproducible evaluation across different translation systems.

However, two decades later, according to the study 'The Results of WMT22 Metrics Shared Task: Stop Using BLEU – Neural Metrics Are Better and More Robust' (Figure 2) [13], it has been demonstrated that neural-based learned metrics are superior; traditional overlap metrics like BLEU, SPBLEU, or CHRF correlate poorly with human ratings.

The results also reveal that neural-based machine translation evaluation metrics are significantly better than non-neural metrics across different domains and chal-

lenges. In order to gather data on translation errors performed by ChatGPT-3.5, ChatGPT-4, and human translators, in the list shown below the COMET-22 and BLEURT-20 were selected.

Metric	avg rank
METRICX XXL	1.20
COMET-22	1.32
UNI TE	1.86
BLEURT-20	1.91
COMET-20	2.36
MATESE	2.57
COMETKIWI*	2.70
MS-COMET-22	2.84
UNI TE-SRC*	3.03
YiSi-1	3.27
COMET-QE*	3.33
MATESE-QE*	3.85
MEE4	3.87
BERTSCORE	3.88
MS-COMET-QE-22*	4.06
CHR F	4.70
F101SPBLEU	4.97
HWTSC-TEACHER-SIM*	5.17
BLEU	5.31
REUSE*	6.69

Figure 2.

Main Results

Using a mixed-method research approach, this study analyzed 30 scientific articles (each contain at least 650 words), sourced from the Acta Naturae journal. [14], These articles translated into Russian language using specific prompts for the ChatGPT-3.5 and ChatGPT-4 models and then compared with human translations. The resulted data (below graphics) were

analyzed using the COMET-22 and BLEURT-20 metrics [15, 16]. The results show that ChatGPT-4 model has improved its performance in translation field comparing with ChatGPT-3.5, which allow to conclude that there is an undoubted improvement in the quality of machine translation based on neural learning. Analyzing these models, which generated scores are roughly from 0-1, for human translation was taken 1 score, where it indicated as a perfect.

BLEURT-20	ChatGPT3.5	ChatGPT4
doc_1	0,303	0,307
doc_2	0,424	0,459
doc_3	0,377	0,412
doc_4	0,02	0,15
doc_5	0,167	0,288
doc_6	0,153	0,256

COMET-22	ChatGPT3.5	ChatGPT4
doc_1	0,840	0,853
doc_2	0,877	0,882
doc_3	0,882	0,878
doc_4	0,663	0,723
doc_5	0,774	0,844
doc_6	0,722	0,782

Many mistakes were found regarding (Doc. 4, 5, 6) for instance:

Original-The reconstruction of the genome of Prince Dmitry Alexandrovich indicates the contribution of three ancestral components to his origin:

Russian version-Реконструкция генома князя Дмитрия Александровича указывает на вклад трех родовых компонентов в его происхождение.

ChatGPT-4-Реконструкция генома князя Дмитрия Александровича указывает на вклад трех **предковых компонентов** в его происхождение.

ChatGPT-3.5- Реконструкция генома князя Дмитрия Александровича указывает на вклад трех **предковских** компонентов в его происхождение;

Original-The existence of a “blind spot” in the study of the genomes of the Medieval Russian

Russian Version: Существование «белого пятна» в изучении геномов древнерусской элиты

ChatGPT-3.5- Существование "темных пятен" в изучении геномов средневековой русской знати;

ChatGPT-4-Существование "слепого пятна" в изучении геномов средневековой русской знати

Original-The location of princely burial grounds is established by annalistic messages, synodics of the XVI–XVII centuries.

Russian Version-Местоположение княжеских погребений устанавливается по летописным сообщениям, синодикам XVI–XVII вв.

ChatGPT-3.5- Место княжеских захоронений устанавливается по **аннальным сообщениям**, синодикам XVI–XVII веков,

ChatGPT-4-Местоположение княжеских захоронений устанавливается по летописным сообщениям, синодикам XVI–XVII веков.

Statistical analysis shows that ChatGPT-4 model translates better in comparison with previous model (i.e) ChatGPT-3.5.

In general, ChatGPT-4 demonstrates high-quality translations in the meaning and choice of a word, in simple extended sentences, and complex sentences as well.

However, the primary errors identified in the comparison between human translated and machine-translated texts include incorrect translations and repetition, non-equivalent and misinterpreted idiomatic expressions. A professional translator, specializing in a specific field, can easily overcome with such difficulties.

Conclusion

In assessing the efficiency of automated translation systems against human translation capabilities, the performance of ChatGPT-4, as quantified by the COMET-22 metric achieves an accuracy of 88% and ChatGPT-3.5 achieves an accuracy of 87%. In the BLEURT-20 metric the performances of ChatGPT-4 and ChatGPT-3.5 models are 45% and 42% respectively.

It should be underlined, that COMET-22 neural fine-tuned metric is a more powerful metric, trained on a wider and more diverse dataset and focusing on the comprehensive semantic similarity between source text and translation. As a result, it is less sensitive to minor errors or deviations in translation. The indicators shown in the schemes above are higher, than those of BLEURT-20.

BLEURT-20 in its turn, is more appropriate for tasks where a high degree of linguistic knowledge and stylistic accuracy is required.

Through the progress in computational linguistics and machine learning, these innovative systems i.e. ChatGPT-3.5 and ChatGPT-4 can interpret and translate the complex nuances of language. However, it's important to remember that automated systems often struggle with idiomatic expressions, cultural references, and the deep context that typically demands human intuition and cultural knowledge. Consequently, while the 88% accuracy rate of ChatGPT-4 demonstrates strong general translation abilities, it also high-

lights the limitations where human oversight and intervention are still necessary in the translation process. We hope that performance of capabilities of neural machine translation systems will improve in the nearest future.

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